

ISic1034

I.Sicily inscription 1034

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

list of

magistrates (?)

Material

tuff

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Found in 1873 during surface survey on the site

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8716

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]Χ
2. [---]προς Ἄρι[---]
3. [Ἀρ]χωνίδας [---]
4. [Ἡρ]ακλείδας [---]
5. [Πο]λύαρχος [---]
- 5a. [---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492662

EDCS 39102188

PHI 140513

PHI 175414

PHI 175625

Bibliography

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Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. *Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi.* In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai.* Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.4a

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